

**LEADERSHIP TRAITS AND PRINCIPALS' ADMINISTRATIVE
EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN EKET
SENATORIAL DISTRICT OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The study examined principals' emotional intelligence as well as integrity and their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South (Eket), Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 63 school principals and all the 1702 teachers of the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South (Eket) Senatorial District. The sample for this study was 340 teachers from the seven LECs selected through the proportional sampling technique which forms 20% of the total number of teachers in each of the LECs. Two research instruments tagged "Principals' Leadership Traits Questionnaire" (PLTQ) and Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ)" were used for data collection. The questionnaires were administered and the data generated in this study were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis (PPMC). All the research questions and hypotheses were tested at a .05 level of significance. The results of the study showed that leadership traits of emotional intelligence and integrity of school principals significantly relate to their administrative effectiveness in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Based on the findings of this work, it was recommended among others that principals should not be appointed only based on their academic qualifications but also based on their leadership traits. Principals should also do everything humanly possible to win the trust of teachers, students as well as parents.

Keywords: Leadership Traits, Administrative Effectiveness, Public Schools, PAEQ, PLTQ.

1 Introduction

The attainment of the goals of any educational institution must be of concern to all the stakeholders. Moreover, considering the nature of man, if principals of public secondary schools fail to effectively carry out their administrative and supervisory duties, most teachers may be ineffective thereby leading to poor performance of students in our public secondary schools and by extension, failure in the attainment of the set educational goals.

Jekayinfa and Kolawole (2008) opined that the main purpose of education, is to develop the individual so that he can be useful to himself, his family, and society generally. Development in this case does not only mean physical development, which we can always see; but it also includes intellectual and emotional development that only manifests themselves in the behaviour and mental activities of the individuals. To ensure that the purposes for which the secondary schools in Nigeria are established are attained, each school principal must possess some leadership traits required for the effective administration of the affairs of the schools.

Sharma (2011) identified the leadership traits (qualities) of a school principal to include communication skills, comfort, empathy, decision-making skill, influence, self-management, time management skills and commitment. Ames and Flynn (2007) categorized these qualities into intelligence, assertiveness (confidence), charisma, and conscientiousness. According to the authors, intelligence has to do with the ability of a leader to be creative in solving interpersonal and work-related problems, being quick in assessing situations and finding solutions. Conscientiousness is the ability to exhibit dedication, steadfastness and willingness to complete work in an efficiently, timely and meticulous way. Charisma on the other hand deals with the ability to motivate others to become enthusiastic about pursuing the goals of the group and the leader acting as a role model. Assertiveness refers to the ability to persist in displaying and defending one's ideas and interests in an unwavering manner and without ambivalence. Other leadership traits or qualities that can enhance effective administrative task performance of school principals are relationships and emotional stability (Lunenburg and Orstein, 2018).

For the purpose of this study, emotional intelligence and integrity will be considered as the leadership traits in relation to the administrative effectiveness of principals in public secondary schools in Eket Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The administration of public secondary schools in Nigeria and in Akwa Ibom state to be precise has become more complex than it used to be as a result of the increase in students' enrolment due to the policy of free and compulsory education, the advent of modern technology and the expanded curriculum (Akpan and Archibong, 2012). To make the situation worse, facilities are in a state of decay with little or no hope for

their replacement. On the other hand, principals tend to contribute to the problem especially when they lack proper coordination and the skills require to maintain the few facilities that the government manages to provide. Sometimes, the principals are accused of negligence, laziness, permissiveness, lack of dedication, and zeal to work (Umosen and Ogon, 2020). It is therefore not out of place to say that lack of leadership traits required of a school principal for the effective administration of our schools is tantamount to poor performance of teachers who are at the centre of the teaching and learning process. Once teachers fail in their duties and students become unserious and disobedient, it means the entire school system is in a state of total collapse. The results of The West African Examination Council and those of the National Examination Council of recent times are obvious pieces of evidence of the fact that school principals are not in control of our secondary schools.

Managing people is not an easy task; there are a number of contemporary issues or problems that school principals face in the course of trying to effectively harness the human/material resources available in public secondary schools towards effective and efficient management of secondary schools. It is against this background that this study investigates the influence of emotional intelligence and integrity on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Eket senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State.

The specific objectives of the study are to find out how:

1. principals' emotional intelligence relates to their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Eket Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom state Nigeria;
2. principals' integrity relates to their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Eket Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom state;

The following are the research questions to guide this study.

1. How does principals' emotional intelligence relate to their administrative effectiveness?
2. Is there a relationship between principals' integrity and their administrative effectiveness?

Five null hypotheses that were formulated to guide the study are:

- HO1. There is no significant relationship between principals' emotional intelligence and their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State.
- HO2. There is no significant relationship between principals' integrity and their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Transformational Leadership Theory-Bass (1985) was considered relevant to the study. Bass defined transformational leadership in terms of how the leader affects followers, who are intended to trust, admire and respect the transformational leader. He identified three ways in which leaders transform followers i. Increasing their awareness of task importance and value. ii. Getting them to focus on team or organizational goals, rather than their own interests. iii. Activating their higher-order needs.

Bass noted that authentic transformational leadership is grounded in moral foundations that are based on four components namely: I. Idealized influence ii. Inspirational motivation. iii. Intellectual stimulation. iv. Individualized consideration.

This theory is related to leadership traits and principals' administrative effectiveness because the main tasks of principals are to motivate, influence, stimulate teachers and help them develop their teaching skills. Moreover, the principals carry out administrative tasks on persons with divergent opinions, beliefs and understanding. As such, the concept of individualized consideration as proposed by Bass in his transformational leadership theory is highly related to traits of leaders that can lead to effective school administration.

2.2 Concept of Administration

Administration is a social process concerned with identifying, maintaining, motivating, controlling and unifying formally and informally organized human and material resources within an integrate system designed specifically to achieve predetermined objectives. Administration has to do with getting things done with the accomplishment of defined objectives (Teddy, 2004). On a broader perspective Administration could be seen as an integral part of any organization. It is crucial for maintaining and expanding the relevance, effectiveness and productivity of complex institutions. Such as Government Department, Prisons, School Systems, Universities among others (Austin, 2009). For example, the survival of all the organizations, like the schools and other institutions is dependent largely on the quality of administrative services available.

Administration, therefore, influences the results to be achieved, the direction to be pursued, and the priorities to be recognized within the organization. Administration, according to Enaohwo and Eferakeya (2009) can be defined as the process by which goals are achieved through collective and cooperative human effort in a suitable environment. This definition specifies four important points: First, administration is a process, which involves the manipulation of certain operations. Second,

administration is goal-oriented. Thirdly, a collective and cooperative human effort is required in administration, and fourthly, a suitable environment, where participants can maximize performance.

It is pertinent to relate administration in the context of education or school organizations. To be able to do that, education administration can be defined as a means of achieving the goals of education through effective and efficient manipulation of available inputs.

Aderounmu and Ehametalor (2005) defined school administration as "essentially a service, activity or tool, through which the fundamental objectives of the educational process may be more fully and efficiently realized". Educational Administration is therefore concerned with the utilization of adequate resources and the harmonization of relationships and interactions in a suitable environment, in order to foster the attainment of the goals of teaching and learning. Educational Administration involves prudent management of resources and high degree of accountability on the part of organizational members. Educational administration broadly means running of educational institutions, which involves guidance, leadership, and controlling of the efforts of individuals in the achievement of the goals of the institution (Ayanniyi, 2000).

Educational Administration also involves management of resources; human, material, and evaluation or appraising of the result of educational efforts. Having explained the concept of educational administration, it will also be wise to briefly explain school administration.

Okereke (2008) stated that school administration involves managing, administering the curriculum and teaching, disciplining, assessment, evaluation, resource allocation, costing and forward planning. The main aim of school administration is to develop an organizational structure, plan and execute an overall strategy for the content and delivery of instruction, maintain the school facilities and maintain liaison with communities, private groups and individuals to whom the school is accountable. (Akpan, 2001).

According to Onoyase (2007), the administrative tasks expected of the school administrator are:

- i. Provision of instructional academic leadership
- ii. Responsibility to staff
- iii. Responsibility to students
- iv. Managing the school's financial and physical resources
- v. Managing the school-community relations
- vi. Keeping of school records. In addition, school administration involves the following:

- I. **Planning:** The school administrators undertake planning in the process of managing the school by assigning teachers to teach various subjects, preparing of time table, and assigning teachers to various post.
- ii. **Organization:** the organization of the school activities by the principal is crucial in order to minimize conflict in the performance of a task by members of staff.
- iii. **Directing:** The school administrator directs the activities of the school by providing good leadership to both members of staff and students. It is significant for a school administrator to provide good leadership in order to achieve the goals and objectives of the school.
- iv. **Budgeting:** The school administrator prepares the annual estimated budgets showing the revenue and expenditure of the school every year. The school administrator indicates in the annual estimate the programs that will be implemented and the objectives of such programs.
- v. **Evaluation:** The evaluation of members of academic staff, non-academic staff and students is an important administrative function of the school administrator. The school administrator needs to be very objective in the evaluation of members of staff since it has great consequences on the promotion of members of staff.
- vi. **Coordination:** The school administrator also needs to coordinate the activities of the school in such a way that all activities in the school are related to one another. The school administrator should ensure that all the members of staff work together as a team.

Sharma (2011) identified the leadership traits (qualities) of a school principal to include communication skills, comfort, empathy, decision-making skill, influence, self-management, time management skills and commitment.

Ames and Flynn (2007) categorized these qualities into intelligence, assertiveness (confidence), charisma, and conscientiousness. According to them, intelligence has to do with the ability of a leader to be creative in solving interpersonal and work-related problems, being quick in assessing situations and finding solutions. Conscientiousness is the ability to exhibit dedication, steadfastness and willingness to complete work in an efficiently, timely and meticulous way. Charisma on the other hand deals with the ability to motivate others to become enthusiastic about pursuing the goals of the group and the leader acting as a role model. Assertiveness refers to the ability to persist in displaying and defending one's ideas and interests in an unwavering manner and without ambivalence.

Other leadership traits or qualities that can enhance effective administrative task performance of school principals are relationships and emotional stability (Lunenburg & Orstein 2008). Relationship deals with the ability to be sociable, sympathetic, cooperative, good-natured, warm and approachable. While emotional stability refers to the capacity for composure, self-confidence and self-awareness.

According to Northouse (2013), the five traits that are central to leadership are integrity, intelligence, sociability, determination, and self-confidence.

Aghenta and Omeregic (2006), posit that the school leader (principal) provides the formal leadership and whose behaviour determines the extent to which teachers see the school as a desirable place in which to work. This suggests that the principal's leadership traits determine the organizational climate of the school and the level of teachers' commitment. Similarly, the leadership traits of the principal determine his effectiveness in the discharge of her administrative tasks. In other words, the principal effectiveness in administrative task performance is a function of his leadership traits. His leadership competence would enable him to induce the teachers and other members of staff not only to participate in school administration but also to commit themselves to the life of the school.

2.3 Concept of Competency in Administration

Competencies are the sum of experiences, knowledge, skills, values and attitudes acquired during the course of doing a job. Olaitan (2003) explained that to be competent the individual must have acquired the knowledge, skills, attitudes and judgment that is required in order to perform successfully at a specified proficiency level in any given work. In the same manner, Hornby (2006) defined competency as the skills an individual needs in a particular job or task. Boyatzis (2008) also defined competencies as a human ability to behave in a way to meet job requirements in parameters given by the organization's environment and thus to achieve the required results. Competency is thus the knowledge, skills, attitudes and judgment acquired through training for a successful, efficient and on-time performance of a task.

Ehrlich, Spote, and Sebring (2016) observed that Principals' competency comprises of a cluster of knowledge, structured in cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains required for carrying out the managerial functions in solving problems and ensuring effective management of schools.

The report stressed the categories of competencies of school principals and grouped them into five.

- i. Develop and Articulate Belief System through Voice and Actions
- ii. Engage and Develop Faculty.
- iii. Assess the Quality of Classroom Instruction.

- iv. Facilitate/Motivate Change.
- v. Balance Management

Administrative competencies are the skills, motives and attitudes necessary for the performance of a job. It includes communication skills, problem-solving ability, customer focus and the ability to work with a team. Skills and knowledge are administrator's competencies that can be measured easily while intangible assets like effective communication and teamwork are harder to pin down and evaluated.

Administrative competencies according to Boyatzis (2008) are activities, knowledge, skills or attitudes and perhaps personal characteristics necessary to improve an administrator's performance. He observed that administrative competencies lead to the demonstration of skills and abilities, which results in effective performance within an organizational environment. Administrative competencies are a specialized subset of competencies that are particularly attributed to the managers of organizations.

Boyatzis (2008) alleged that outstanding administrators like school principals require this subset of competencies such as threshold clusters of competencies which include expertise and experience, knowledge, and an assortment of basic cognitive competencies. Schools also need clusters of competencies to differentiate outstanding from average performers such as cognitive competencies, emotional intelligence competencies and social intelligence competencies. Boyatzis opined that administrative competencies are the specific attributes and capabilities that illustrate a principal's management potential. The knowledge and skills of principals should therefore be developed and matched with their current and future planned roles in an organization. Their competencies are based on recognizable work activities.

Katz (2015) identified three administrative competency skills essential for successful administration. These are technical, human, and conceptual skills. In school organization, the technical skill involves the principal's understanding of the nature of the job that people under him have to perform to achieve the stated objectives. Human skills involve the ability of the manager to interact with people while conceptual skills deal with the formulation of ideas, conceptualization of abstract and complex situations. Relating these skills to the study, principals should be able to see the schools as a whole, understand the relationship among various sub-units, and visualize how schools fit into their environment. In this study, the current operational practices of Principals will be investigated to determine the extent of their managerial competencies in the five areas of administration namely supervision of instruction, personnel management, finance management, school plant maintenance and school-community relationship.

The teacher chooses the best method suitable for the subject matter, students' ability, available materials and time based on his or her own capacity. To the extent that this is achieved, showed the extent of the administrative competencies of the school administrator which the principal is at the head of affairs. Principals' competencies are embedded in their administrative functions through the use of adequate skills needed in the supervision of instruction in public secondary schools. Principals' administrative competencies in the supervision of instruction involve the Principal's participation in the classroom through adequate monitoring, providing teaching aids and offering professional advice to teachers for improvement during actual teaching. In the views of Quinn (2002), principals are responsible for informing teachers about new educational strategies, technologies and tools that apply to effective instruction.

3 Methodology

3.1 Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 63 principals and all the 1702 teachers of the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District).

In this research, teachers were used to examine principals' leadership traits as well as their administrative effectiveness. The choice of the respondents was informed by the fact that the teachers are under the leadership of the school principals and are in the best position to provide information on their leadership traits and how such traits relate to their administrative effectiveness in the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District).

3.2 Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for this study was 340 teachers from the seven Local Education Committees (LEC) comprising 63 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State. The sample was selected using the proportional sampling technique. 20% of the total number of teachers in each of the Local Education Committees (LEC) were selected as a sample. Based on this technique, seventy-eight (78) teachers were sampled from Eket Local Education Committee (LEC), eighty-one (81) teachers from Mkpato Local Education Committee (LEC), thirty-five (35) teachers from Ikot Abasi Local Education Committee (LEC), forty-seven (47) teachers from Onna Local Education Committee (LEC), thirty-eight (38) teachers from Oron Local Education Committee (LEC), twenty-one (21) teachers from Mbo Local Education Committee (LEC) and forty (40) teachers from Okobo Local Education Committee (LEC).

3.3 Instrumentation

The study was carried out using a four-point scale questionnaire. The instruments tagged "Principals' Leadership Traits Questionnaire" (PLTQ) and Principals'

Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ) were developed by the researcher. The questionnaires elicited information on principals' leadership traits of emotional intelligence and integrity and their administrative effectiveness from the respondents (teachers).

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

The data generated in this study were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis (PPMC). All the hypotheses were tested at a .05 level of significance.

3.5 Decision Rule

In answering the research questions and testing the hypotheses, if the calculated r-value is greater than the critical r-value, the null hypotheses were rejected. On the contrary, if the calculated r-value is less than the critical r-value the null hypotheses were retained.

4 Results and Findings

4.1 Answering of Research Questions:

Research Question One: How does principals' emotional intelligence relate to their administrative effectiveness in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District?

To answer this research question Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis was employed, and the data obtained are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis for the relationship between leadership trait of emotional intelligence and principals' administrative effectiveness.

Variables	$(\Sigma X)(\Sigma Y)$	$(\Sigma X^2)(\Sigma Y^2)$	ΣXY	r.cal
Emotional Intelligence(x)	5691	98103	281893	.703
Principals' Admin. Effectiveness (y)	16500	816282		

Entries in Table 1 reveal the relationship between emotional intelligence and principals' administrative effectiveness. The result shows that the calculated r-value of .703 is very strong. This means that there is a high positive relationship between emotional intelligence and principals' administrative Effectiveness in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Question Two:

How does principals' integrity relate to their administrative effectiveness in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District?

To answer this research question Pearson Product Moment Correlation was employed, and the data obtained is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis for the relationship between leadership trait of integrity and principals' administrative effectiveness

Variables	$(\Sigma X)(\Sigma Y)$	$(\Sigma X^2)(\Sigma Y^2)$	ΣXY	r-cal
Integrity (x)	5733	99397	283959	.738
Principals' Admin. Effectiveness (y)	16500	816282		

Entries in Table 2 reveal the relationship between integrity and principals' administrative effectiveness. The result shows that the calculated r-value of .738 is very strong. This means that there is a high positive relationship between integrity and principals' administrative Effectiveness in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.2 Testing the Null Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' emotional intelligence and their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3: The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis for the relationship between emotional intelligence and principals' administrative effectiveness.

Variables	N	ΣX ΣY	ΣX^2 ΣY^2	ΣXY	r.cal	r.crit	df	sig
Emotional Intelligence(x)	336	5691	98103	281893	.703	0.095	334	sig

Principals' admin
Effectiveness(y) 336 16500 816282

Predictor: Principals' Emotional Intelligence; dependent variable: Principals' administrative effectiveness *Significant at .05 level; N= 336; critical-r 0.095

Table 3 shows that the calculated r-value of .703 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.095 at 0.05 significance level with 1 and 334 degrees of freedom. The result is significant; therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between principals' emotional intelligence and their administrative effectiveness is rejected in favour of the alternative one. The result means that there is a significant relationship between principals' emotional intelligence and their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant relationship between principals' integrity and their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis for the relationship between integrity and principals' administrative effectiveness.

Variables	N	ΣX ΣY	ΣX^2 ΣY^2	ΣXY	r.cal	r.crit	df	sig
Integrity(x)	336	5733	99397	283959	.738	0.095	334	sig

Principals' admin
Effectiveness(y) 336 16500 816282

Predictor: Principals' Integrity; dependent variable: Principals' administrative effectiveness *Significant at .05 level; N= 336; critical-r 0.095

Table 4 shows that the calculated r-value of .738 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.095 at 0.05 significance level with 1 and 334 degrees of freedom. The result is significant; therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between principals' integrity and their administrative effectiveness is rejected in favour of the alternative one. The result means that there is a significant relationship

between principals' integrity and their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

4.3.1 Principals' Emotional Intelligence and Their Administrative Effectiveness

The result shows that there is a significant relationship between principals' emotional intelligence and their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State.

This is in line with Goleman (2006) who observed that leaders with high emotional intelligence are key to organizational success and that leaders must have the capacity to feel employee's emotions in their work environment, intervene when problems arise, manage their own emotions in order to gain the trust of employees and to understand the political and social conventions within an organization. Likewise, Rosete and Ciarrochi (2013) conducted a small exploratory study of the relationship between the ability to measure emotional intelligence, personality, cognitive intelligence and leadership effectiveness amongst senior executives. The Correlation analyses revealed that higher emotional intelligence was associated with higher leadership performance.

Cherniss and Goleman (2001) explained that an emotionally intelligent principal will have a greater effect in his school than a principal with a low level of emotional intelligence. Without any iota of doubt, emotional intelligence is an integral part of the school management process; and, if a principal expects to guide his school in the right direction, he needs to be able to deal effectively with emotions. Goleman, et.al (2002) confirmed that great leaders have the ability to work through emotions. In his opinion, Fullan (2003) observed that effective leaders combine a strong sense of moral purpose, an understanding of the dynamics of change, and great emotional intelligence as they relate with their subordinates. Apart from this, secondary school principals must be able to influence and understand relationships and the feelings and emotions of those they serve and lead. This is because, if a leader is not sensitive to his own feelings, it may be difficult for him also to be sensitive to the feelings of the people around him and this will ultimately affect their relationship.

Rosete and Ciarocchi (2013) revealed that leaders' ability to perceive their own emotions has a significant relationship with leadership effectiveness and leaders' actual performance. The results also indicate that leadership's ability to perceive other people's emotions is a predictor of leaders' performance. Caruso, Salovey and Mayer (2003) asserted that principals need emotional intelligence to be successful in their schools. It implies that a school leader needs to be emotionally intelligent so as

to possess conflict resolution skills. Moreover, Fullan (2005) emphasized that emotionally intelligent leaders are aware of their own emotional makeup, sensitive and inspiring to others, and are able to deal with day-to-day problems in the workplace.

4.3.2 Principals' Integrity and Their Administrative Effectiveness.

The finding of the study revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between integrity and principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This is corroborated by the view of Shahid (2013) who said that integrity is the authentication of a person who displays strong moral and ethical principles at work. In the same vein, Ekosiswoyo, (2016) Said that Principals who have integrity will gain trust from their fellow teachers, students, parents, and other stakeholders. He further stated that a principal who has integrity has the following characteristics: (i) trustworthy; (ii) consistent; (iii) commitment; (iv) be responsible; (v) have emotional intelligence.

In the Turknett Leadership Character Model—developed by psychologist Dr. Robert Turknett, integrity is the foundation of the model, and without integrity, no leader can be successful. The Turknett Leadership Group notes that individuals with integrity will not twist facts for personal advantage; they are willing to stand up for and defend what is right; they will be careful to keep promises; and they can be counted on, to tell the truth. In their model, integrity is the foundation of leadership and it involves a careful balance between respect and responsibility (Turknett, 2009). The trait of a high-integrity principal is that she/he is capable of giving motivation, inspiration, and empowerment to teachers, students, and staff members. Integrity is honesty, credibility, and consistency; a leader must place these values into her/his actions. To Bernard, Schurink and De Beer (2008), in integrity there are attitudes like self-motivation and drive; moral courage and assertiveness; honesty; consistency; commitment; diligence; self-discipline; responsibility; trustworthiness and fairness. Basically, integrity makes leaders trustworthy and worthy of our trust (Northouse, 2013).

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

Considering the findings of this study, it is evident that principals' leadership traits of emotional intelligence and integrity significantly relate to their administrative effectiveness in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State.

Based on these findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are presented:

1. Since principals' administrative effectiveness to a great extent is influenced by their level of emotional intelligence, school principals should ensure that they think critically before making decisions concerning their schools.
2. The school principals should make sure that teachers, students as well as parents can trust them. This is very important because the principals' integrity contributes immensely to their administrative effectiveness. A principal with integrity will always have the support of his staff and the parents in whatever decision he/she takes and will contribute voluntarily to the growth and development of the school.

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